

Evaluation of the Education Management Performance of an Effective School Principal

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Abstract:

In this article, the management performance evaluation criteria of the general secondary school principals have been reviewed, and the foreign experiences in evaluating the effectiveness of school principals' managerial activities. In addition, the criteria for evaluating the education management performance of an effective school principal have been proposed.

Keywords: *School principal, Management performance, Evaluation, Evaluation criteria, School leadership.*

Introduction

At present day, various methods of evaluating the professional performance of school principals are widely studied all over the world. The existence of a perfect, logical, and theoretically proven assessment system allows one to manage personnel development, identify hidden reserves, and eliminate shortcomings in education.

However, both in our country and foreign countries, there are occurred great challenges in solving the issue of evaluating the managerial activities of the managers of educational institutions. In particular, the experience of the certification of the faculty staff shows that most countries face great difficulties in deciding on awarding the first and highest qualification categories to the person who deals with the title of management. This is mainly since, taking into account the specific characteristics of educational development, no scientifically evident requirements have been imposed on the heads of educational institutions until now; a

system of comprehensive indicators, criteria, and procedures for evaluating the professional qualities, management skills, and labor efficiency of the leaders of educational institutions has not been developed. As a result, the performance evaluation of the leaders of educational institutions in different regions is carried out using methods that cover only some aspects of management skills. This leads to the fact unclearness of transparency of the performance evaluation of the school principals in different regions.

Therefore, the importance of evaluating the activities of the leading personnel of educational organizations - school principals, to increase the effectiveness of their management skills becomes a prior task. The Decree PF-5538 of the President of our country "On additional measures to improve the public education management system", dated September 5, 2018, emphasizes that there are no specific criteria and parameters for evaluating the performance of school principals, (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5538, 2018) as

well as in the Presidential Decree No. PF-134 “On Approval of the National Program for the Development of Public Education in 2022-2026”, dated May 11, 2022, has ensured the significance of developing the criteria and determination of strategic directions for evaluating advanced school principals’ performance and managerial skills (Decree No. PF-134 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2022).

We believe that evaluating school principals’ performance is critical to improving their managerial career, building their capacity, increasing accountability for teacher effectiveness and student progress, and ensuring that they have an overall positive impact on students school staff, and the community. Taking into account the link between effective school principals and student achievement, the evaluation and development of school principals’ management competence should be progressively recognized as a key strategy for improving schools, growing student achievement, and closing persistent achievement gaps.

Literature Review

Within this research topic, scientific research works of C. Condon, M. Clifford, R. Heck, T. Larsen, G. Marcoulides, R. Vanderbergh, H. Ebmeier, J. Kouzes, B. Posner, K. Leithwood and others have studied and analyzed.

Research Methodology

In the preparation of the article, at the theoretical level – to review kinds of literature and analyze scientific-methodical manuals regarding to the scientific problem of the research, and, at the empirical level pedagogical experience, observation methods, interviews, questionnaires, and statistical methods of information processing were used.

Analysis and Results

All over the world to develop school education, many scientific and practical activities have been carried out on reforming the school principals’ managerial career. World scientists develop the criteria for evaluating the school principal’s activity based on the standards of the school principal’s educational leadership.

In Europe, the *Interstate School Leaders Licensure Consortium (ISLLC) - Policy Standards for Educational Leadership* have helped guide school principals since they were developed in 1996 by the Interstate School Leader Licensing Consortium.

The ISLLC standards consist of six standards of functions that help define strong school leadership (Educational Leadership Policy Standards: ISLLC., 2008).

Standard 1: The school administrator is an educational leader who promotes the success of all students by facilitating the development, articulation, implementation, and direction of a vision of education that is shared and supported by the school community.

Standard 2: The school administrator is an educational leader who promotes the success of each student by advocating, nurturing, and sustaining a school culture and curriculum that supports student learning and staff professional growth.

Standard 3: The school administrator is an educational leader who promotes the success of every student by ensuring the management of the organization, operations, and resources for a safe, efficient, and effective learning environment.

Standard 4: A school administrator is an educational leader who promotes the success of every student by collaborating with faculty, family, and community members, and mobilizing community resources.

Standard 5: A school administrator is an educational leader who ensures the success of each student by acting in honesty, fairness, and ethical manner.

Standard 6: A school administrator is an educational leader who promotes the success of every student by understanding, responding to, and influencing the larger political, social, economic, legal, and cultural context.

Depending on the content of the ISLLC standards, scales were created by the world scientific community to evaluate the management skills of school principals. In particular, the following 8 rating scales were found to be effective in a study conducted by the staff of Learning Point Associates (Condon & Clifford, 2012):

1. Change the Facilitator Style Questionnaire. Vandenberghe developed the Change Facilitation Style Questionnaire (CFSQ) to assess the extent to which leaders can facilitate change. The CFSQ identifies three different approaches to facilitating change: initiator, manager, and responder. The data is divided into three clusters, each cluster includes two measurements:

Cluster 1. Concern for people (attitude): scale 1 (social/informal) and scale 2 (formal/meaningful)

Cluster 2. Organizational Effectiveness: Scale 3 (Trust in Others) and Scale 4 (Administrative Efficiency)

Cluster 3. Strategic perception: scale 5 (Daily activities) and scale 6 (Vision and planning future activities) (Vanderberghe, 1988).

2. Diagnostic Assessment of School and Principal Effectiveness. Ebmeier developed this measure to identify the strengths of schools and school principals and to better inform school improvement plans and key professional development goals. Individual surveys are completed by students, teachers, parents, and principals to complete the evaluation. Indicators show how these groups relate to themselves, school leadership, and school activities. Several activities are conducted by several groups to determine the fit between school leader characteristics and school characteristics. These measures can be used separately depending on their purpose (Ebmeier, 1992).

3. Instructional Activity Questionnaire. This assessment, developed by Larsen, examines the instructional leadership aspects of school principals' work. It was developed through an extensive literature review on school principal effectiveness (Heck, Larsen, & Marcoulides, 1990).

4. Leadership Practices Inventory - Conduct extensive interviews and surveys with leaders, including principals, to identify the best leadership practices using the Couse and Posner Leadership Practices Inventory (LPI). Thus, the LPI believes that leadership practices are transferable to professional types. What inspires people in a business environment can also work in an educational sphere. The domains of the LPI are (1) path modeling, (2) shared vision inspiration, (3) challenging the process, (4) enabling others to act, and (5) motivation. This scale is common across many disciplines. It can also be completed online or as a printed survey on the LPI (Kouzes & Posner, 2002).

5. Performance Review Analysis and Improvement System for Education (PRAISE) was developed by Knoop and Common through conducting an extensive literature review on the effectiveness of school administration. The PRAISE assessment questionnaire consists of 81 assessment items with 9 sub-criteria including problem-solving, relationships with teachers, professional qualities, and competencies, for answering them 15-20 minutes are set (Knoop & Common, 1985).

6. Principal Instructional Management Rating Scale. Hallinger and Murphy (1985) developed the Instructional Management Rating Scale (PIMRS) to measure the level to which principals serve as instructional managers. The PIMRS also provides examples of each construct that can be used by raters to identify changes in their own or others' practice. PIMRS focuses on several constructs, including the use of time for instructional improvement, curriculum alignment, and instructional evaluation (Hallinger, 1994).

7. Principal Profile. The Principal Profile was developed through extensive interviews and consultation with principals, teachers,

inspectors, and heads of department. The authors consulted with practitioners to determine validity and reliability and to ensure that the assessment was practical for use in school/district settings. It consists of two main assumptions: (1) student growth should be a criterion for school leader effectiveness and a factor in performance evaluations, and (2) school leader effectiveness is determined by the consistency of action, as principals are expected to follow clearly defined goals and achieve them consistently. Skills and knowledge are required to achieve (Leithwood & Montgomery, 1986).

8. Vanderbilt Assessment of Leadership in Education (VAL-ED) - Since its development in 2006, the Vanderbilt Assessment of Leadership in Education has become one of the most widely used criteria for evaluating school leadership. VAL-ED evaluates principal performance by collecting information from principals, teachers, and vice-principals. VAL-ED results create a quantitative diagnostic profile linked to ISLLC standards. Also, VAL-ED is intended to annually (or more often) evaluate the effectiveness of school principals, to guide professional improvement. Respondents are asked how effective the principal is at specific actions that affect key components of a student-centered leadership system. For each of the 72 criteria in the questionnaire, efficiency ratings are assigned from 1 (not effective) to 5 (very effective) (Vanderbilt Peabody College, 2012).

According to the analysis, a distinctive feature of school leadership reforms in Europe is that they rely on the ISLLC standards for both assessing and ranking principals and developing principal professional portfolios.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Research on effective schools, shows that principals of educationally effective schools strive to maintain a strong connection between schooling goals, technology, and outcomes. Based on this, we propose to divide the educational management role of an effective school principal into three general criteria: defining the school's mission, managing the

educational process, and promoting a positive learning environment.

These include an additional 10 education management tasks.

Defining the school's mission:

- 1) Formation of school goals
- 2) Delivering school goals

Management of the educational process:

- 3) Control and evaluation of the instruction (school road map).
- 4) Coordination of the curriculum
- 5) Monitoring the development of students

Promoting a positive learning environment at school:

- 6) Protection of study time
- 7) Promotion of professional development
- 8) Keeping a high profile (school image).
- 9) Motivating teachers
- 10) Stimulating learning

Based on the above criteria, we consider that it is possible to achieve the quality of education through the quality of management by eliminating the deficiencies in management in time and solving the problem promptly.

References

- Council of Chief State School Officers. (2008). *Educational Leadership Policy Standards: ISLLC*. Washington, DC.
- Condon, C. & Clifford, M. (2012). *Measuring Principal Performance How Rigorous Are Commonly Used Principal Performance Assessment Instruments? A Quality School Leadership Issue Brief*
- President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2018). Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5538 "On additional measures to improve the public education management system", Tashkent.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2022). Decree No. PF-134 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026", Tashkent.

Ebmeier H. (1992). *Diagnostic assessment of school principal effectiveness: A reference manual*. Topeka, KS, Kan LEAD Educational Consortium Technical Assistance Center.

Heck, R. H., Larsen, T. J., & Macrolides, G. A. (1990). Instructional leadership and school achievement: Validation of a causal model. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 26(2), 94–125.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X90026002002>

Knoop, R., & Common, R. W. (1985, May). *A performance appraisal system for school principals*. Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of the Canadian Society for the Study of Education, Montreal, Quebec, Canada.

Kouzes, J., & Posner, B. (2002). *Leadership Practices Inventory: Theory and evidence behind the five practices of exemplary leaders*. Unpublished document.

Leithwood, K.A., & Montgomery, D. J. (1986). *Improving principal effectiveness: The principal profile*. Toronto: OISE Press.

Philip Hallinger, Patchanee Taraseina, Jack Miller, (1994). Assessing the Instructional Leadership of Secondary School Principals in Thailand. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 5(4), 321-348.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/0924345940050401>

Vanderburgh, R. (1988). *Development of the questionnaire for assessing principal change facilitator style*. Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of the American Educational Research Association, New Orleans, LA.

Vanderbilt Peabody College, February, 2010. *Development of the Vanderbilt Assessment of the Leadership in Education*. (VAL-ED). Nashville, TN.